

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.
Privacy policy.

Deliverable 2.1 Data Management Plan

KitNewCare

Authors: Bridget Johnston (BJ); Brett Duane (BD); Anita Griffin (AG);

Technical references

<i>Project Acronym</i>	KitNewCare
<i>Project Title</i>	Developing a framework/model to environmentally sustainable and climate neutral health and care systems using the Kidney care pathway
<i>Project Coordinator</i>	Brett Duane Trinity College Dublin (TCD) Brettdu@tcd.ie
<i>Project Duration</i>	January 2024 – December 2027 (48 months)

<i>Deliverable No.</i>	D2.1
<i>Dissemination level*</i>	PU
<i>Work Package</i>	WP 2 – Knowledge Database
<i>Lead beneficiary</i>	Trinity College Dublin (TCD)
<i>Contributing beneficiary/ies</i>	Icons, Unimore
<i>Due date of deliverable</i>	30 June 2024
<i>Actual submission date</i>	30 June 2024

- * PU = Public
PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

v	Date	Beneficiary	Author
1.0	13/05/2024	TCD	Brett Duane, Bridget Johnston, Anita Griffin

Document Control Information

Settings	Value
Document Title:	Deliverables 2.1 Data Management Plan
Project Title:	KitNewCare
Document Author:	Bridget Johnston/Brett Duane/Anita Griffin
Project Coordinator	Brett Duane (PI) & TCD Team (PCT)>
Project Manager:	Anita Griffin
Doc. Version:	1
Sensitivity:	<Public, Limited, High>
Date:	30/06/2024

Document Approver(s) and Reviewer(s):

NOTE: All Approvers are required. Records of each approver must be maintained.

Reviewers will review the document in accordance with the
KitNewCare_v2.Deliverables_Acceptance_Plan_Ethics_14-03-2024

Name	Role	Action	Date
Brett Duane	Co-Author	Approve	17/06/24
Anita Griffin	Co-Author	Approve	18/06/24
Bridget Johnston	Co-Author	Approve	17/06/24
Lucy Brown	Reviewer	Approve	16/06/24
Inge Steinbach	Reviewer	Approve	24/06/24
Alessandra Calzarossa (ICONS)	Reviewer	Approve	24/06/24

Document History

The Document Authors are authorised to make the following types of changes to the document without requiring that the document be re-approved:

- Editorial, formatting, and spelling
- Clarification

To request a change to this document, contact the Document Authors.

Changes to this document are summarised in the following table in reverse chronological order (latest version first).

Revision	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes
V1	10/06/24	Bridget Johnston/Anita Griffin/ Brett Duane	

Configuration Management Document Location

The latest version of this controlled document is stored in [KitNewCare Deliverables](#)

Table Of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1 INTRODUCTION	6
1.1 Deliverable Purpose and Scope	7
1.2 Target Audience.....	7
1.3 Methodology and Structure of the Deliverable	8
2 DATA SUMMARY	9
2.1 Anticipated activities related to data	9
2.2 Data related to scientific publications	11
2.3 KitNewCare Public Deliverables	16
3 FAIR DATA	17
3.1 Making data findable	17
3.2 Making Data Accessible.....	19
3.3 Making data interoperable	21
3.4 Making data reusable	21
4 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	22
5 DATA SECURITY	23
5.1 Intellectual Property Rights	23
5.2 Data storage	23
6 ETHICS	24
7 OTHER ISSUES	25
8 CONCLUSIONS	26
ACRONYMS	27
APPENDIX	29

Executive summary

Effective data management is crucial for Research and Innovation (R&I) projects. It ensures the structured collection, storage, organisation, sharing, and maintenance of data through established procedures. This approach enhances data accessibility, performance, and timeliness.

This document, deliverable D2.1 from Work Package 2 (WP2), outlines the Data Management Plan (DMP) and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) protection procedures. It details the data lifecycle for datasets collected, processed, or generated during the project.

The DMP serves as a vital project output, providing a comprehensive plan for ~~i~~ KitNewCare's data activities. This includes data gathering/generation, storage, processing, and sharing throughout the project and beyond. The DMP adheres to the Horizon Europe Guidelines on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) Data Management and utilises the European Commission's DMP template as a foundation.

The DMP is a living document, subject to regular updates throughout the project lifecycle. Updates are triggered by significant changes, such as new data regulations or consortium policy revisions (e.g., data sharing scope, de-identification practices, backtracing, or anonymisation). A detailed Data Management Plan (DMP, D2.1) will be delivered by M6, reviewed in M24 (mid project) and again M42 (6 months before the end of the project).

Data will originate from various sources:

- Existing information
- Project activities
- Data from trusted partners, external evaluators, and third-party beneficiaries

This DMP establishes a comprehensive strategy for handling all data and project documentation related to these sources. Datasets will be anonymised for research and impact assessment purposes.

All personal data will be processed in strict compliance with REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016. Access will be restricted to authorised users who have undergone a validation process.

List of Contributors

Contributors to this deliverable are outlined in Table 1.

Table 1 Contributors to deliverable 2.1

Name	Organisation	Contribution
Anita Griffin	TCD	Co-Author
Bridget Johnston	TCD	Co-Author
Brett Duane	TCD	Co-Author
Sofia Finzi	Icons	Reviewer
Lucy Brown	CSH	Reviewer

Co-funded by the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

1 Introduction

Data Management Plans (DMPs) are a key element of good data management. A DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated through a research programme's activities. As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable (FAIR), a DMP should include information on:

- Data summary
- FAIR
- Other research outputs
- Allocation of resources
- Data Security
- Ethics
- Other issues
- The handling of research data during & after the end of the project
- What data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- Which methodology & standards will be applied
- Whether data will be shared/made open access and
- How data will be curated & preserved (including after the end of the project)

Research and innovation projects like KitNewCare can generate vast amounts of data, encompassing diverse information from laboratory tests to field research and scientific observations. The specific data originates from the project's field of study and can be voluminous in nature.

KitNewCare fosters open collaboration, with partners contributing valuable information through Open Access (OA) channels. This includes open datasets, open-source coding, scientific publications/white papers, and anonymised survey results.

However, it's crucial to strike a balance between open information sharing and safeguarding sensitive data. Each consortium member needs to actively manage this equilibrium.

Open access to research findings fosters transparency and scientific progress. However, adherence to General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) remains paramount. Mishandling sensitive data can lead to legal repercussions.

1.1 Deliverable Purpose and Scope

The KitNewCare Data Management Plan (DMP) serves as a living document, a comprehensive record, documenting data handling practices throughout the project lifecycle – from inception to completion. The four-year KitNewCare project is expected to generate a wealth of data that will be crucial for further deployment efforts.

This report outlines how data will be handled within KitNewCare. The project involves three main data types:

1. Data gathered from stakeholders during programme activities (users and service providers).
2. Publications and databases generated through programme activities.
3. Existing data collated and utilised during programme activities.

This DMP fulfils three key objectives:

1. **Data Quality and Reusability:** Define standards for proper data management, encompassing encapsulation, editing, version control, and preservation. This ensures data quality and facilitates future reuse for verification purposes.
2. **Data Organisation and Access:** Outline the methods for determining data classification (public or confidential), organising, curating, storing, and disseminating the data generated, processed, and collected during the project.
3. **Ethical and Legal Compliance:** Guarantee that all data management practices align with current and future ethical and legal regulations.

By addressing these objectives, the DMP fosters responsible data stewardship throughout the KitNewCare project.

1.2 Target Audience

The target audience for this deliverable is:

1. Partners and Advisory Group in the KitNewCare project
2. European Commission

3. EU Parliament
4. Other Horizon Europe or Sustainable Healthcare related projects (clustering activities)
5. Organisations and experts involved in the KitNewCare case studies
6. Other relevant organisations (both public and private), including associations of relevant stakeholders

1.3 Methodology and Structure of the Deliverable

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data and data used for collateral activities such as communication and dissemination are created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

The document follows the established Horizon EU template for a Data Management Plan (DMP) and covers the domains:

- Anticipated activities related to data generation, collection and processing across the KitNewCare programme.
- How data and metadata will be made FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable reusable.
- Anticipated resource allocation requirements, security arrangements, ethical considerations and any other related issues.

2 Data Summary

KitNewCare aims to help healthcare providers and decision makers reduce pollution, carbon emissions, and waste, and improve care pathways, using kidney care as a test case. Collecting data from stakeholders, partners and external contributors is crucial to achieving this.

2.1 Anticipated activities related to data

KitNewCare is expected to generate, collect and process a variety of data. This includes publicly accessible data and internal operational data which are mostly generated and collected by the partner entities, including information of pilot and research organisations. Anticipated data sources for the KitNewCare project include:

- Academic and grey literature;
- Primary qualitative and quantitative research activities with relevant stakeholders;
- Public databases;
- Data from KitNewCare dissemination, promotion and branding activities (e.g., website traffic, visitors and other website analytics, webinars participants).

During the initial months of the project, activities are focused on identifying relevant care pathways and collecting data to assess their impact on four factors: environmental, social, financial and health outcomes. This will be done in a number of ways including workshops to map care pathways, environmental life cycle assessment of inputs and products, interactive discussions with stakeholders and systematic evidence synthesis.

Other core activities and deliverables aim to develop training and implementation initiatives and establish the project website. As the programme develops, additional activities will come online, all aimed at engaging stakeholders to identify hotspots and innovative solutions in relation to kidney care pathways. Additionally, evaluation of KitNewCare results might imply involving “real personas” (citizens outside consortia partners). Should this be the case, their personal data will always be anonymised.

As currently planned at this stage of the programme, there are five work packages that will generate new data and/or utilise existing data as part of core activities:

- WP2 will generate new data and utilise existing data sources to create a four-factor database that maps the environmental, social, financial and health outcomes associated with relevant kidney care pathways

- WP3 will utilise existing data sources and data generated across other KitNewCare activities to train staff, identify areas for service improvement, test changes and sharing best practices across different healthcare centres.
- WP4 will utilise existing data sources to identify and test environmentally friendly technologies for kidney care. Innovation challenges will generate new data, identifying the most promising solutions, followed by piloting these technologies. The project will then utilise data generated in WP2 to evaluate the environmental, social, financial, and health outcomes impacts of the successful solutions and share them with other healthcare facilities.
- WP5 will generate new data and utilise data from WP2 in developing a Dashboard tool to measure how sustainable kidney care practices are. The tool will consider health outcomes, environmental impact, financial costs, and social value. The project will then pilot this tool and explore its use in other areas of healthcare.
- WP6 will collect new data for dissemination, promotion and branding activities (e.g., website traffic, visitors and other website analytics, webinars participants).

Table 2 provides an indicative dataset overview based on current and planned activities, focusing on the data types, origin, format and respective work package for the expected data.

Table 2 Indicative overview of datasets

Data type	Origin	WP#	Format (indicative)
Stakeholder contacts	Public data, Primary data	1-7	.xls, .pdf
Environmental, cost, health outcomes and social impact data	Public data, Primary data	2,4,5	.xls, DALYS CO2 equivalent
Stakeholder interview data	Primary data	2,5	.doc, mp4, .pdf
Quantitative survey data	Primary data	2,5	.xls, .csv, .pdf, JSON, ZOLCA

Any interactions with service users and key stakeholders intended to generate new data will be done only after the signing of informed consent forms and mainly in the form of (individual or focus group) interviews, interactive workshops or quantitative surveys. Since the interest of KitNewCare is in large-scale trends rather than in individual responses, the feedback or input provided from individuals (which can be attributed directly to them and therefore constitutes personal data) will be aggregated into statistical or pseudonymised qualitative datasets.

Personal Data collected by the WP Leader for dissemination, promotion and branding activities collected through the website or specific events are collected based on the Data Controller Legitimate Interest and are treated following the Data Controller Privacy policy.

Audio recordings will be generated and saved within the closed OneDrive/Teams environment only, and will only be stored in this format until transcription and validation has been completed. All transcription data will be generated and saved within the closed OneDrive/Teams environment only. Quantitative datasets and any transcripts generated through qualitative research methods will also be stored in OneDrive/Teams only.

The expected size of the data is not known currently, most likely for each work package it would be under 50 GB.

All KitNewCare partners will regularly provide detailed information in tabular form about datasets they employ as the respective project activities are developed and implemented (both primary generation and re-use). This includes the type of data, its origin (where it comes from), the relevant work package number, and the format it will be stored in and the size of associated files.

The environmental footprint data will be made available at site-level to project partners. It is presently envisaged that any other new data generated will only be made available in anonymised or pseudonymised format to project partners that require it for the purposes of the project, specifically to create statistical and aggregate data. No further use is planned, although the data conceptually may be useful to scientific researchers interested in validating or repeating the research.

2.2 Data related to scientific publications

The project will follow an open access approach for data dissemination. Data reusability procedures are described in Section 3. According to the European Commission, (see also Article 29.2 of the GA), the KitNewCare Consortium will adhere to the EU open access to publications policy, choosing open access self-archiving (hereinafter also referred to as 'green' open access), namely “a published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript is archived (deposited) in an online repository before, alongside or after its publication. Repository software usually allows authors to delay access to the article ('embargo period')”. Wherever possible, KitNewCare will prioritise ‘gold’ open access, which entails publishing directly in open access journals or publicly funded repositories.

This dataset will comprise manuscripts reporting the scientific work conducted across KitNewCare which have been accepted for publication in peer-reviewed journals and conferences. These manuscripts or outputs may (and likely will) contain aggregate and statistical data, and describe key findings from KitNewCare activities, but no personal data will ever be included. All these publications will include a statement with acknowledgement to the KitNewCare project.

Most commonly, these documents will be stored in PDF format. Each document will be also accompanied by: (a) details about the venue (e.g. conference, workshop or benchmarking activity) or journal where it was published, (b) a short description with the abstract of the publications, and (c) the LaTeX-related BIB file with its citation. This dataset will be extended whenever new submitted works are accepted for publication in conferences or journals.

This dataset will be publicly available in OpenAIRE or Zenodo, following the guidelines of the EC for open access to scientific publications and research data.

Self-archiving (also known as "green" open access) will be applied for ensuring open access to these publications. According to this archiving policy, the author(s) of the publication will archive (deposit) the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in online repositories, such as personal webpage(s), the project website and the free-of-charge OpenAIRE or Zenodo repositories, after its publication. The archiving policy will also be fully aligned with restrictions concerning embargo periods that may be defined by the publishers of these publications, making the latter publicly available in certain repositories only after their embargo period has elapsed.

Table 2 Types of data collected, justification for collection and associated processing activities in KitNewCare

Data Collected	Justification	Processing Activity
Participant names	Identification	Excel database, situated in a secure and dedicated OneDrive folder accessible only to the study team at the relevant clinical site. The file will be password protected. The 'Protect current sheet' function will be used to control the types of changes that can be made to this data.
Participant email address	To allow the research team to contact volunteering participants	Excel database, situated in a secure and dedicated OneDrive accessible only to the study team at the relevant clinical site. The file will be password protected. The 'Protect current sheet' function will be used to control the types of changes that can be made to this data.
Participant telephone number	To allow the research team to contact volunteering participants	Excel database, situated in a secure and dedicated OneDrive accessible only to the study team at the relevant clinical site. The file will be password protected. The 'Protect current sheet' function will be used to control

		the types of changes that can be made to this data.
Participant postal address	Ethical basis for proceeding - participants may choose to have the information letter and consent form sent to them by post.	Excel database, situated in a secure and dedicated OneDrive accessible only to the study team at the relevant clinical site. The file will be password protected. The 'Protect current sheet' function will be used to control the types of changes that can be made to this data.
Written consent	Legal/ethical basis for proceeding	Signed documents will be stored in a secure and dedicated OneDrive project folder accessible only to the study team at the relevant clinical site and Horizon EU project staff at TCD.
Audio recordings	To allow the research team to fully capture all qualitative data provided during interviews with participants.	Audio recordings will be taken during the interview and stored in a secure and dedicated OneDrive accessible only to the KitNewCare study team. Audio recordings will be permanently deleted from OneDrive at the end of the grant programme.
Transcriptions	To allow the research team to identify, analyse and collate participants' views and preferences related to the environmental footprint associated with kidney care pathways	Audio recordings will be transcribed by a member of the research team and stored in a secure and dedicated OneDrive project folder accessible only to the study team. The transcripts will be password protected to ensure confidentiality. Personal data will be removed after transcription and kept in a codebook file. The transcripts will be analysed using NVivo software, a cloud-based programme. The analysis file will be password protected.
Survey forms	To allow the research team to identify, analyse and collate participants' views on views and preferences related to the environmental footprint associated with kidney care pathways	Excel database, situated in a secure and dedicated OneDrive accessible only to the study team at the relevant clinical site. The file will be password protected. The 'Protect current sheet' function will be used to control the types of changes that can be made to this data.

Table 3 Measures to protect the confidentiality of personal data collected through KitNewCare primary research activities

Personal/sensitive data type	Media Format	Storage Details
Participant names	Electronic database	Excel database (password protected), situated in a secure and dedicated OneDrive cloud-based folder accessible only to the study team at the relevant clinical site. Team members will only access these data using encrypted devices approved by their institution. The 'Protect current sheet' function will be used to control the types of changes can be made to any data file with participants' personal data.
Participant email addresses	Electronic database	Excel database (password protected), situated in a secure and dedicated OneDrive cloud-based folder accessible only to the study team at the relevant clinical site. Team members will only access these data using encrypted devices approved by their institution. The 'Protect current sheet' function will be used to control the types of changes can be made to any data file with participants' personal data.
Participant postal addresses	Electronic database	Excel database (password protected), situated in a secure and dedicated OneDrive cloud-based folder accessible only to the study team at the relevant clinical site. Team members will only access these data using encrypted devices approved by xx. The 'Protect current sheet' function will be used to control the types of changes can be made to any data file with participants' personal data.
Participant telephone numbers	Electronic database	Excel database (password protected), situated in a secure and dedicated OneDrive cloud-based folder accessible only to the study team at the relevant clinical site. Team members will only access these data using encrypted devices approved by their institution. The 'Protect current sheet' function will be used to control the types of changes can be made to any data file with participants' personal data.

Consent forms	Soft copy	Signed document stored in a secure and dedicated OneDrive cloud-based folder accessible only to the study team at the relevant clinical site and Horizon EU project staff at TCD. Team members will only access these data using encrypted devices approved by TCD.
Consent forms	Hard copy	Stored in a locked cabinet at the relevant clinical site. Only study team members at the site will have access to the forms.
Audio recordings	Electronic file	Audio recordings will be password protected and stored in a secure and dedicated OneDrive cloud-based folder accessible only to the study team at the relevant clinical site and Horizon EU project staff at TCD. Team members will only access these data using encrypted devices approved by their institution.
Transcriptions	Electronic file	Transcriptions will be stored in a secure and dedicated OneDrive project folder accessible only to the study teams at the relevant clinical site and Horizon EU project staff at TCD. The transcripts will be password protected. Personal data will be removed and kept separately in a codebook. Pseudonymised transcripts will be analysed using NVivo software, utilising the cloud-based features for continuous storage. The analysis file will be password protected.
Survey forms	Hard copy	Stored in a locked cabinet at the relevant clinical site. Only study team members at the site will have access to the hard copy forms.
Survey forms	Electronic file	The database containing pseudonymised survey responses will be password protected and stored in a secure and dedicated OneDrive cloud-based folder accessible only to the study team at the relevant clinical site and Horizon EU project staff at TCD. Team members will only access these data using encrypted devices approved by their institution.
Codebook	Electronic file	Personal data will be removed for transcriptions and kept in a password protected Excel database. The codebook will be stored in a secure and dedicated OneDrive

		project folder accessible only to the study team at the relevant clinical site.
--	--	---

2.3 KitNewCare Public Deliverables

All KitNewCare public deliverables will be available on the project website KitNewCare.eu for public access. These deliverables are made available in PDF format after approval by the Project Officer (PO) at the end of the reporting period.

Each deliverable will consist of:

- Author list
- Summary: A brief description of the content.
- Work Package (WP) that this deliverable is associated with.
- Due date: The date the deliverable was originally planned for submission to the European Commission (EC).

Data Included in Public Deliverables:

- Public deliverables may contain anonymised and statistically analysed data.
- Information about user personas (fictional representations of target users) may be included but will not contain any personal data from co-creation sessions.
- No personal data from co-creation sessions will be included in the public deliverables.

The project website will have a dedicated webpage where you can find a list of all public deliverables. Each deliverable will be listed with a link to its .pdf file, ensuring easy access.

3 FAIR data

Fair data use, in the context of European Commission projects, revolves around the **FAIR Data Principles**. FAIR stands for:

- **Findable:** Data should be easy to discover for both humans and machines. This is achieved through clear and comprehensive metadata using common vocabularies and searchable online resources.
- **Accessible:** Data should be readily available to authorised users under clear and documented conditions. This may involve access controls and restrictions based on privacy or sensitivity, but there should be a process for obtaining access.
- **Interoperable:** Data and metadata should use standardised formats that allow them to be combined and analysed with other datasets. This ensures compatibility and avoids issues when integrating information from different sources.
- **Reusable:** Data should be well-described with clear licensing terms that specify how others can reuse it. This allows researchers and innovators to build upon existing data and create new knowledge.

Following the FAIR principles makes data more valuable and promotes knowledge sharing within the research community. The European Commission encourages and often mandates FAIR data practices in Horizon EU and other research funding programs.

3.1 Making data findable

The KitNewCare project ensures research data is easily found and understood.

- **Internal Data:** All project data is stored in a central Teams folder, accessible to all partners.
- **Public Data:** Public-facing data is on the project website, optimised for search engines using relevant keywords. The website may include specific sections for individual pilots in the future.
- **Data Description:** Partners provide detailed descriptions (metadata) for each data set to make it easier to find, understand, and reuse. This metadata includes:
 - Descriptive information (title, summary, creator, keywords)
 - Administrative details (creation date, file type, access rights)
 - Content details (subject terms, reference period, project funding info)

- Release information (dissemination rules)
- Data collection details (source, location, language, format)

KitNewCare would assign persistent and globally unique identifiers (such as DOIs) to all datasets and processes within its database. These identifiers would be prominently displayed and easily accessible to users.

Consortia partners will provide adequate metadata for relevant data sets in order to ease the interpretation of the data and to increase their identification, discoverability, re-use and preservation. Metadata is structured information describing the characteristics of the sources. A distinction is made between:

- Descriptive metadata, such as title, abstract, author, and keywords,
- Administrative metadata which are used to provide information to help manage a source, such as when and how it was created, file type and other technical information, and who can access it.

In order to increase findability, partners will also include keywords or key-phrases describing the subject or content of the data including relevant disciplinary and general standards and terms for metadata ensure their quality, consistency, and credibility. Key resources include those provided by ISO (International Organisation for Standardisation) in the ISO 14040 series¹, and the EU's own PEF standards².

Other information contained in the research data includes the reference period, project funding information (e.g. EU logo and information about the Grant Agreement and the action/program that funds the project, official project name and project ID), release policy including dissemination rules, information about the collection of the data such as the data source, geographic coverage of the data, language, and file format.

KitNewCare will utilise two approaches to support harvesting and indexing:

1. **Persistent Identifiers:** Assign persistent identifiers (e.g., Digital Object Identifiers - DOIs) to datasets to ensure long-term accessibility, discovery and use. Persistent identifiers enable indexing systems to uniquely identify and link to specific datasets, enhancing discoverability and traceability across different platforms and repositories.
2. **Machine-Readable Formats:** Offer metadata in machine-readable formats such as XML, JSON, or RDF to facilitate automated harvesting and processing by indexing systems. Machine-readable formats enable indexing systems to parse metadata efficiently and extract relevant information for indexing purposes.

¹ **ISO 14040:**2006 covers life cycle assessment (LCA) studies and life cycle inventory (LCI) studies.

² The European Commission proposed the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) method as a common way of measuring environmental performance

The choice to make metadata offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed will be made on a case by case basis, drawing on input from stakeholders across the project consortium. Key guiding principles include:

- Addressing privacy concerns: Metadata might contain sensitive information that should not be made widely accessible.
- Ensuring security: Making metadata harvestable could introduce security vulnerabilities, especially if it exposes internal information about stakeholders' or users' system.
- Maintaining appropriate control where required: There might a need to control exactly how some metadata are used and displayed, which could be eroded through harvesting.

3.2 Making Data Accessible

The KitNewCare project follows its consortium agreement and relevant funding guidelines for dissemination of materials. Public deliverables (marked "PU" in the project description) will be openly available on the project website. Additionally, these materials may be shared on platforms like Zenodo and OpenAIRE, following the Grant Agreement and Open Access guidelines.

Zenodo is a multi-disciplinary open repository maintained by CERN. Datasets, documents and other research materials can be located via the Zenodo search engine. Scholars from any research discipline can upload data in any file format. A digital object identifier (DOI) is automatically assigned to all Zenodo files.

KitNewCare will host also relevant data on a dedicated project website. This platform will serve as a centralised hub where users can freely access and download datasets, processes, and related resources without any barriers to entry: www.KitNewCare.eu

Open research data will be available without requiring login or identification. By removing authentication requirements, KitNewCare ensures that the data are readily available to anyone with an internet connection, regardless of their institutional affiliation or geographic location. However, to protect participants and encourage open communication, all reports and communication will use pseudonymised or anonymised data. Original identifiable data will be stored securely for research validation and follow-up but kept separate from anonymised data and accessed only according to strict confidentiality and security protocols.

Certain data fall outside the scope of the open access strategy. These include raw qualitative research data from interviews, focus groups and workshops; raw quantitative data from surveys; draft reports and presentations; preliminary or unfinished analyses; project meeting notes and internal communications; plans for future research or grant applications; and raw peer reviews.

- Raw qualitative research data from interviews, focus groups and workshops (including audio recordings, code books and transcripts)
- Personal data of participants, partners, or stakeholders
- Raw quantitative survey data (any identifiable data)
- Internal project drafts, unfinished work, and personal notes
- Future research plans or grant applications, preliminary analyses, and peer reviews
- Informal communication outside of research activities

To ensure privacy, any data included in public deliverables will be anonymised. This means:

- Qualitative data (including recordings, code books and transcripts) will only be released in pseudonymised, aggregate formats.
- Survey results will only be reported in aggregate, statistical formats.

This anonymisation protects the identities of users, companies, administrations, and Member States. Original identifiable data will not be openly accessible, but source information will be retained for legal or project-related purposes. Such storage will be organised separately from the research data and in adherence to suitable confidentiality and security standards. In cases where data are closed but there are no compelling reasons that the related metadata should not be findable and accessible, open access will be provided to the metadata of the data, with CC0 public domain dedication or equivalent, if possible, while the dataset itself remains closed.

Our KitNewCare research data will be securely preserved for the long-term using Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>), a leading solution in the research community. While Zenodo isn't formally certified yet, it adheres to best practices for data storage and accessibility. They are committed to future certification of their systems. Zenodo automatically assigns and signposts a DOI to all uploaded materials.

While we're currently using OneDrive and our website for data storage in this project's early stages (5 months old), we have a long-term plan to migrate everything to Zenodo. This free-to-use platform ensures our research outputs are permanently accessible, easily shared, and properly cited. Zenodo caters to various scientific data formats, making our findings discoverable by a wider research community in the long run.

3.3 Making data interoperable

It is anticipated the metadata structure will utilise the DCAT-AP specification. Data will be provided in field/domain specific standards and formats, where applicable. The final list of relevant standards has yet to be determined by Consortia members.

The vocabulary used in the project is a very standard and common language within environmental impact assessment, healthcare systems and kidney care. Vocabulary and terminology will not represent any barrier for data interoperability and re-use.

3.4 Making data reusable

The project's data will be promptly released on the KitNewCare website, appropriate communication channels and storage platforms such as Zenodo. All public and private entities will have access rights, enabling them to duplicate, share, or modify the data.

All open research data will be made available for re-use without any data embargo, meaning that all data will be made openly available and free to re-use upon their publication. Furthermore, definitive decisions in relation to the publishing/sharing of data with regards to licenses and point in time can only be decided upon once the selection of data sources has been finalised and thoroughly evaluated.

Data will remain accessible for use in the long-term through Zendodo. The Consortium is also committed to keeping the data usable for as long as feasible through the website following the project's completion. An initial duration of six years for the project website has been set; nonetheless, this period could be extended with the agreement of the partners.

4 Allocation of resources

During the project, the data will be stored in Zenodo's infrastructure at no cost for the consortium. This ensures there are no post-project funding requirements and maximises data accessibility beyond the lifetime of the project.

The lead coordinator of KitNewCare (TCD) will be primarily responsible for overseeing data management activities. TCD will coordinate and supervise the implementation of data management plans, ensuring compliance with project objectives, ethical standards, and regulatory requirements. Additionally, they will liaise with project partners, data producers, and stakeholders to facilitate data sharing, documentation, and dissemination efforts throughout the project lifecycle. Partners retain responsibility for implementing procedures to recover the data they generate.

5 Data security

5.1 Intellectual Property Rights

The KitNewCare project prioritises strong IPR management to optimise project outcomes and innovation. This involves identifying intellectual property (datasets, software, etc.) and its associated rights. An internal structure manages background and project-generated IPR, with details provided in Work Package 6 (Task 6.3: Consolidation of the Exploitation Plan). The Consortium Agreement outlines partner rights and responsibilities regarding IPR ownership and exploitation. This ensures clarity and protection throughout the project lifecycle.

IPR Management plan Background IP remains with original owners. Foreground IP will vest in the partner that generated these results. Collectively developed foreground will be jointly owned. All rights and obligations – including (shares) of ownership, management issues and costs arising from legal protection will be regulated in the Consortium Agreement. All partners contribute to the identification of results that may qualify for IPR protection to optimise outcomes in line with the call topic

5.2 Data storage

All data will be stored following the procedures for data storage at Trinity College Dublin, utilising Teams and OneDrive platforms. Sensitive data will be stored and accessed via secure Teams and OneDrive platforms in compliance with GDPR and national legislation.

Data will only be shared outside the EU with our non-EU partner, the UK. In this case data protection in the UK will be governed by the Data Protection Act 2018. The UK has implemented appropriate GDPR in line with EU policy and has been recognised by the EU as having an adequate level of personal data protection. The TCD's Data Protection Officer will ensure these governance standards are followed.

6 Ethics

The ethical aspects of the KitNewCare project will be assessed under Work Package 7, which sets out the ethics requirements that the project must comply with, and includes 8 separate deliverables, each addressing a specific topic.

Key obligations and constraints assumed by the project include:

1. The appointment of an external, independent Ethics Advisor; with relevant expertise in medical research ethics and data protection, was appointed in Month 1 to advise and oversee the activities involving research participants and related data aspects
2. The definition of standardised procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants;
3. The definition of standardised information and consent templates and procedures for any data collection activities with research participants;
4. Emphasis on the voluntary nature of participation in the study;
5. Explanation of the duration and effort required for participation in any activity;
6. Clarification of withdrawal rights, with the ability to request the destruction of any personal data;
7. Provision of contact information for project stakeholders;
8. A description of relevant security and confidentiality measures;
9. The definition of an anonymisation and pseudonymisation strategy;
10. A general assessment of ethics risks other than data protection challenges.
11. The following Ethics Deliverables dealing with data security have been submitted:

Deliverable 7.4 An external independent Ethics Advisor, with relevant expertise in medical research ethics and data protection, was appointed in Month 1 to advise and oversee the activities involving research participants and related data aspects.

Deliverable 7.1 Vulnerable individuals will be involved: kidney patients who may be in a dependent position and could be exposed to coercion or undue inducement.

Deliverable 7.3 Beneficiaries must clarify whether anonymisation or pseudonymisation techniques will be used on any personal data gathered in the project

7 Other issues

This section will be expanded in future versions to include specific data management procedures mandated by national regulations, funders, or relevant industry/departmental standards.

8 Conclusions

This document outlines the KitNewCare project's data management strategy. It provides an initial analysis of potential data sources, including those generated by the project consortium and those used for project activities. The scope of project results encompasses all project-related information, such as scientific publications, white papers, open-source code, open datasets, anonymised/pseudonymised interview results, or mock-up datasets employed to gather feedback.

The current version of the report identifies research data associated with the project's work packages. This data is categorised based on its accessibility (public or sensitive/confidential) and managed accordingly. The KitNewCare Data Management Plan adheres to the FAIR Data Management principles set forth by Horizon Europe, ensuring data findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.

This document will be continuously updated throughout the project lifecycle. The Data Management Plan (DMP) will be revised whenever significant developments occur, including the introduction of new data, innovations, consortium member changes, and other relevant updates.

Acronyms

ACRONYMS	DEFINITION
AAKP	American Association of Kidney Patients
BIB	Abbreviation of Bibliography
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC0	Creative Commons Zero
CKD	Chronic Kidney Disease
CSH	Centre for Sustainable Healthcare
DCAT-AP	Data Catalogue Application Profile
DEC	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
EDTNA	European Dialysis and Transplant Nurse Association
EEI	Events Engagement Index
EKHA	European Kidney Health Alliance
EPF	European Patients Forum
ERA	European Renal Association
ERA-EDTA	European Renal Association - European Dialysis and Transplant Association
ESCOs	Energy service companies
ESHN	European Sustainable Healthcare Network
EU	European Union
EWOPA	European Working Group on Psychosocial Aspects of Children with Chronic Kidney Disease
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISN	International Society of Nephrology
KDIGO	Kidney Disease, Global Outcomes
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisation

PEF	Product Environmental Footprint (PEF)
PEI	Publication Engagement Index
PPI	Patient and Public Involvement
PPT	PowerPoint
QI	Quality Improvement
R&D	Research and development
SEI	Social Engagement Index
SME	Small, Medium Enterprise
SRL	Societal Readiness Level
TCD	The Provost, Fellows, Foundation Scholars & The Other Members of Board, Of The College of The Holy & Undivided Trinity Of Queen Elizabeth Near Dublin
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UMCU	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht
WEEI	Webinar Engagement Index
WEI	Website Engagement Index
WP	Work Package
WUM	WARSZAWSKI UNIWERSYTET MEDYCZNY

APPENDIX

Appendix 1: References and Related Documents

ID	Reference or Related Document	Source or Link/Location
1	KitNewCare .v2.Deliverables Acceptance Plan Ethics 14-03-2024	KitNewCare .v3.Deliverables Acceptance Plan Ethics 14-03-2024_vIS.docx
2	ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf (europa.eu)	ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf (europa.eu)
3	Ethics Deliverable 7.1	KitNewCare_V2_Ethics Deliverable 7.1_14_03_2024.pdf
4	Ethics Deliverable 7.3	KitNewCare_V2_Ethics Deliverable 7.3_14_03_2024.pdf
5	Trinity College Dublin: Research Data Management - The Library of Trinity College Dublin - Trinity College Dublin (tcd.ie)	https://www.tcd.ie/library/riss/research-data.php
6	Data Management Plan – Horizon Europe	https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm
7	Ethics and Data Protection Tree	GDPR - Decision tree reviewed (europa.eu)
8	Product Environmental Footprint (PEF)	https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/EnvironmentalFootprint.html
9	ISO 14040 series	https://www.iso.org/standard/37456.html ISO 14040 series

Co-funded by the European Union

**UK Research
and Innovation**

